

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF SILENCE IN THE PROCESS OF SPEECH COMMUNICATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7423922>

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ELSEVIER

Received: 10-12-2022

Accepted: 11-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

Abstract: The article gives opinions on the development of students' speech communication competences, and details the importance and necessity of silence and non-verbal means in the communication situation.
Keywords: silence, expressive effect, non-verbal means, inappropriate silence, facial expressions, unhealthy environment.

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As we study the topic of the development of speech communication competence, silence has a special place in it. The reason is that this happens in the process of communication. It can be said that in a dialogic situation, its weight and importance in the situation increases. Silence when a person sits alone cannot be called silence. Sukut is actually a word that came from the Arabic language, and it can be connected with the words of silence, silence.

Silence (or silence) refers to "the omission of a word or group of words at the end of a sentence." In the literature, silence is interpreted as a form of ellipsis. We can observe that this method is used in the artistic text for the following purposes. Usually, the hero's silence (remaining silent) is marked by many points. However, it should not be forgotten that not all sentences with multiple periods are examples of silence. Sometimes the author himself explains the silence of the hero and the reason for it. In this situation, the expressive effect drops to an imperceptible level. [1.78]

Loneliness is better than a bad conversationalist.

A righteous conversationalist is better than loneliness.

It is better to speak well than to sit still.

It is better to be silent than to speak evil words. (Hadith). [2.56]

Silence is simply being silent in a speech situation, that is, a multipoint in dialogic speech in a written situation. However, in a speech situation, this single silence can express a number of broader meanings than the one indicated by the nonverbal means.

"In communication, even silence (being silent, not speaking) participates as a non-verbal tool and expresses a specific communicative content. Of course, unlike a word or a sentence, silence may not express meaning outside of the communication process, i.e., in sleep and similar situations. Therefore, the linguist scientist M. Saidkhanov divides silence into types that have communicative content and non-communicative content, Siddiq Mominov adds. - It is known from our observations that silence in the process of dealing in many nations expresses similar meanings. For example, if the Uzbek saying "Silence is a sign of consent" is exactly the same as the Russian saying "Molchanie - znak soglasiya", the German saying "Non-answering is the answer" is very similar to the meaning of the Uzbek proverb "The answer to a fool is silence". . But as "The real life of the word is in the text" (A.A. Potebnya), silence is also clearly known in the process of natural communication". [3.50]

Silence is very important in fiction. And our writers use it effectively in their creations. As an example, we can witness the effective use of silence in many places in the well-known work of Abdulla Qadiri, "Otkan Kunlar".

Especially, in the column "I didn't like the air of Margilan" of the first part, the conversation between Hasanali and Otabek comes like this:

Otabek had to turn his face away from Hasanali, who was staring at him. It was as if this old magician could read all the secrets from the page. Knowing that Hasanalini was still staring at him, he frowned.

"Well, go on..."

"You want to hide this secret from me," said Hasanali with complete satisfaction, because now he was very confident in his discovery. - Well, maybe you have the right to hide... but is it possible to achieve any result by keeping it a secret?

- ...

Otabek was blushing crimson and looking at the ground like a sinner. Hasanali's face was filled with a look of tarahhum, and with a special melodious sound for the elderly, he began to take the heavy load on the back...[4.13]

There is a saying in our people: The sign of silence is consent. However, it is a big mistake to always look at it as a sign of consent. In fact, it can be said that this proverb appeared through some of our traditions that are characteristic of the Uzbek mentality. For example, suitors come to a house where there is a girl child and ask for her hand in marriage. The mother puts her hand on her daughter's bosom and tells the situation. At this point, if the girl likes it, she will look at the ground in shame without any objection. This means that he has no resistance.

However, it performs different functions in different situations. Take, for example, a young child's bullying of his parents...

Despite saying no, the mother's silence instead of an answer to her son, who asked to go to the mountain with his friends, cannot be called a "sign of consent".

Or, in a completely different situation, the boy who sent the suitor to the girl, the people in the house of the girl, who want to know about the future groom's manners, behavior, and lineage, want to ask the next-door neighbors about the future groom. And the neighbors' answer is silence...

Now, if we return to the art of public speaking in the discussion of our topic, a person who is speaking in public often keeps a little silence during communication. This can be understood as an opportunity for the listeners to digest the ideas.

Educators also make good use of silence during class. And this silence alone will serve to end the chaos of the students and take control of the situation. Or in some places it is necessary to be silent at some point in order to increase the impact of the speech.

Silence occurs not only among speakers, pedagogues, lecturers, but also among people in other fields due to the requirement of professional communication. Let's take doctors for example: When the operation ends unsuccessfully, they explain the situation to the patient's relatives by silence without being able to tell them about it at once (you can see a lot of images of this situation in movies and clips). But there are professionals who cannot remain silent. Khurshid Davron says about this: "The most terrible silence is when a poet walks silently." [5]

A student who is taking a step into public speaking will definitely need to understand these concepts correctly and use silence appropriately during communication. However, it is necessary to distinguish between appropriate and inappropriate silence. Sometimes the students "answer" the questions asked by the teachers by default. This shows the lack of knowledge of the students on this topic.

Inappropriate silence should not become the biggest defect in a child, or even a defect. When will this happen? If a child is under the influence of an unhealthy environment at a young age, or if he is reprimanded for everything he says, or if he is under pressure for everything he does, or in general, if the child is not properly approached in education, the child will feel inappropriate silence.

Here is an example of a story:

A child was born in a household. At a young age, he heard from someone that all trouble comes from one's tongue, and he got into the habit of not speaking at all because he was afraid.

There is no physician whose parents have not shown concern about this. In this way, the boy grew up and one day the father began to look for birds in the forest to teach his growing son how to hunt. At that moment, a bird flew out and they shot it down. Seeing this, the boy looked at his father:

"That's why I don't talk, father." "If this bird had not opened its mouth, it would have lived a long time," he said.

The father looked at his son in surprise:

"Yeah, aren't you dumb yet?" Why didn't you speak until now?!, he slapped his face. Sometimes, as above, it is necessary to emphasize about the students who have a habit of keeping silent more than the norm: "If you keep silent, the world will keep silent for you." That is: "O man, if you remain silent, those who have not heard your voice will not know whether you exist or not, they will forget you in the end. As a result, the world will forget you. Therefore, live happily.

In religious and some secular sources, silence is equated with a "good word", a "sign of intelligence". For example, in the Holy Qur'an there is such a verse: "... let the believer speak good words or keep silent" or "He who keeps silent will be saved", "The wrestler who knocks down everyone is not strong, but he who catches himself when anger comes (keeps silent) There are hadiths such as "a person is strong".[6.140]

That's why it is necessary to take a special approach to solving such problems, which are often encountered in the speech of schoolchildren, in mother tongue classes. And in the process of working on the text, in the questions and answers, serious attention should be paid to this issue. After all, "Just as expressing an opinion at the right time is a great art, keeping silence at the right time is not a funny art either". However, we cannot say that it belongs only to the group of non-verbal means. Because non-verbal means are facial expressions, behavior, tone, eye gaze, gestures, which in a certain sense indicate the emotional state of the speaker. In particular, through these non-verbal means it is possible to understand things like joy, happiness, pain, hatred, happiness, sadness... About this f.f.d. M. Saidkhanov writes: "There are different opinions about the use of non-verbal means as a means of communication and intervention, the reasons for their use by mankind. Those who believe that facial expressions and other speech-filling means involved in communication are a natural-biological phenomenon say: "Non-verbal means are an ancient form of communication-interaction between people".[8.17]

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